

Medicalization of childbirth and postnatal care. The contemporary need for a natural approach to childbirth.

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Abstract

Medicalization is a process by which natural events inscribed in the life of every human being are treated as medical problems that require diagnosis and control, with emphasis on pathology and treatment. Childbirth is a natural phenomenon, not a medical one, which is why medical intervention is not necessary in a properly running childbirth. The situation is different in Poland, because hospitals treat births routinely. Various equipment to facilitate childbirth will be presented and described in this article. Furthermore, the acceleration of childbirth, routine medical procedures as well as possibility of taking any position during the first and second period of childbirth will be discussed.

Keywords: : medicalization, development, cells, anatomy

By means of the medicalization of delivery, we mean performing unnecessary medical procedures routinely during delivery, often without justification and clinical indications and supposedly to help in the birth of a child. These procedures include puncture of the membranes of the fetus to speed up labor and "massage" of the cervix - one of the more painful habits of the staff assisting in childbirth. At the outset, one should ask the following question: Does the medicalization of deliveries result from concern for the safety of the child or is it dictated by the convenience of medical personnel? Many procedures performed during the admission of the patient to the emergency room, and later to the delivery room are performed on the stock assuming that delivery is a pathological phenomenon requiring strict control. Just in case, a woman at the hospital's threshold receives a venflon, oxytocin, she is permanently attached to a CTG, she has to lie down and everything is done so that the delivery is not a physiological and natural act, but routine, predictable and quick. Why let a woman drink water during delivery when you can give her a drip? Why wait for the onset of childbirth when it can be induced? Who would follow the recommendations of 2-hour contact with the newborn baby *skin to skin*, since it is more important for the hospital staff to wash and weigh the child? Such examples can be multiplied.

Acceleration of childbirth

A separate place in the field of the medicalization of childbirth is the *acceleration of childbirth* and in particular the intensification of contractile function through the intravenous infusion of Oxytocin. For the proper course of labor, a systolic function is needed, but intervals between contractions are equally important. It is during the

break of the interval that the fetus is ready to improve its oxygenation. During contraction, the blood flow through the uterus is minimal, because the vessels supplying blood to the placenta run between the fibers of the uterine muscle. Oxytocin, used at the wrong moment, also increases the resting tension of the uterine muscle, which may paradoxically prolong the opening of the cervix and certainly affects the painful perception of uterine contractions by the mother [1], [2].

Childbirth *accelerated* can be compared to another acceleration procedure. To speed up walking in the mountains.

No doubt most healthy people have enough strength to walk in the mountains. But let's try to run in the mountains. Instead of a few kilometer walk, a nice trip, our trip will end after only a few hundred meters and instead of relaxation we will find fatigue. Similarly, mother, in the name of helping her, is often subjected to "accelerated" delivery instead being allowed to go through the physiological course of childbirth, perhaps longer but certainly less painful and less exhausting. In some cases of *accelerating* energy and physiological reserves are exhausted before childbirth and as a result in the patient's chart there are indications for caesarean section such as *no progress of labor, exhaustion of labor*. Undoubtedly, the physiological reserves of the fetus are also limited [3]. The next *accelerating childbirth* procedure is sometimes used in the second period of delivery (thankfully, less and less often), Kristelera procedure, is squeezing the fetus from the uterus. The time of birth of the head is reduced, but probably at the expense of pelvic floor muscle damage and vaginal cracks, non-physiological pressure increase in the skull of the

emerging baby and possible complications and even dramatic final such as rupture of the uterus or the laboring liver [3].

Properly performed crotch incision and subsequent its skillful sewing is beneficial for many births and certainly better than extensive crotch injury without incisions and abnormal supply. However, the routine incision of the crotch and various additional annoyances such as the absence of anesthesia of the crotch before its incision should be eliminated [3,4].

Routine medical procedures

Another problem that sometimes affects the mother and the fetus or the newborn baby is performing certain activities, examinations and medical procedures whose purpose is not to improve the patient's well-being, but to create records for the medical documentation. Here are some examples:

1. Routinely performed or unnecessarily extended of the KTG record and long-term immobilization of the female patient connected to the medical apparatus.
2. Invasive monitoring of fetal scalp blood gasometry. Blood gasometry in a healthy newborn baby.
3. Routine assessment of the *fetal water color*.

The delivery of medicaments is also a routine use of anesthesia in the childbirth process. We can choose from a whole range of techniques of analgesia of delivery: from biophysical methods such as water immersion or percutaneous electrical nerve stimulation (TENS), through intravenous administration of painkillers up to the ductal (epidural or even subarachnoid) anesthesia. There is no doubt that giving birth without pain is a tempting alternative but one has to accept the fact that not every woman requires analgesia. Often the symptoms are moderate and you can avoid routine use of analgesia or give it at birth. Any method of analgesia applied too soon or in the wrong patient may result in a longer duration of delivery or a negative effect on the newborn's condition. Often analgesia during childbirth, especially epidural anesthesia and sometimes pharmacological agents, are not given to those patients who require them. Similarly, water immersion is an unquestionable achievement in the field of analgesia as well as psychotherapy and relaxation during childbirth, and accelerates its course accordingly. A beautiful perspective but often only for a lucky few [5].

According to the latest report of the Foundation *Rodzić po Ludzku*, a physiological childbirth is treated as an event requiring multidimensional medical assistance [1].

Here are the most important conclusions from the report entitled *Medicalization of childbirth in Poland*.

- **hospital childbirth** - Over 99% of children in Poland are born in hospitals. In 2015, there were 370,026 births in hospitals (of the total 370 706

births), 680 newborns were born outside the hospital, including 136 deliveries at home.

- **induced births** - 19% of all births in the surveyed hospitals were induced births. According to WHO recommendations, it should not exceed 10%. Induction of labor increases the probability of more painful spasms, the need for epidural anesthesia or caesarean section.
- **natural births with crotch incision** - The percentage of perineal incisions has been maintained in Poland for 50% for years. It is a high figure compared to other European countries.
- **childbirth with stimulated systolic action** - WHO recommends that such childbirth should be no more than 10%. Based on data received from hospitals in Poland, this takes place in 25% of childbirths. The most commonly (87%) used medication given to women is oxytocin. It says in the Foundation's report the results show that administering oxytocin to stimulate contraction action increases the percentage of caesarean cuts, births with epidural anesthesia and antenatal fever among primiparas and multiparous women.
- **KTG** - in 9% of nursing hospitals women are connected to the CTG throughout the duration of the delivery, which prevents them from changing position from lying on more favorable births. Only 13% of hospitals declare that during physiological labor the KTG record is only used every 2 hours.
- **internal examination** - in accordance with perinatal care standards, internal examination should not be performed more frequently than every 2 hours. The report shows that only 17% of Polish hospitals respect these standards. Midwives examine internally on average every 103 minutes, and doctors every 109 minutes.
- **caesarean section** - 43% of pregnancies end with a caesarean section. It is much more than 10% recommended by the WHO.
- **a drip in a physiological birth for the purpose of hydration is given in 35% of hospitals** - despite the fact that almost all hospitals declare that they allow babies to drink fluids. This is inconsistent with both WHO recommendations and perinatal care standards.
- **childbirth lying down** - in Polish hospitals, positions that obstruct the physiological course of delivery are still most commonly used. The most often used positions are on the side and on the back.
- **cutting the umbilical cord before the cessation of the ripple** - 94%. Hospitals adhere to this recommendation, in 6% of facilities it is cut off immediately.
- **skin to skin contact** - only 32% of hospitals adhere to the right to uninterrupted two-hour *skin to skin* contact. Most often, it is disturbed

by weighing, measuring and dressing a newborn baby.

- **hospital conditions** - in more than half of hospitals women still give birth in multi-person rooms which are worse equipped than single rooms. In 10% of them there is not a single piece of equipment helpful in the childbirth (ball, mattress). In 49% of hospitals all births take place in single-person rooms. Although there are fewer single-person rooms, over half of births in Poland take place there.
- **the person providing care** - only every fourth hospital fulfills the rule found in perinatal care standards, according to which a woman can choose a carer from among the entitled persons. In 77% of hospitals in Poland, the person providing care is allocated without the patient's participation.
- **pharmacological methods of pain relief** - inhalation analgesia is most often used (84%) followed by epidural anesthesia (49%) and pethidine (30%). However, accessibility declarations do not coincide with the actual use of these methods. In 2015 in only 51% of births inhalation methods were used, in 40% lumbar anesthesia and in 13% pethidine. Epidural anesthesia will not be provided in 32% of hospitals (no anesthetist). The easiest access to epidural anesthesia in the Małopolskie voivodship (88% of hospitals) and in Silesia (85%), and the most difficult in Wielkopolskie and Lubuskie (38%) and Podkarpackie (36%), where the highest percentage of cesarean cuts in Poland is performed.
- **hospital admission** - women are asked about a childbirth plan in 54% of hospitals, in 26% you need a referral to the hospital, and 21% a proof of health insurance. 7% of hospitals still require a certificate of completion of a course at a birth school.
- **education** - only 14% of hospitals do not have or do not cooperate with any birthing school. 67% of birthing schools offer classes free of charge [5].

Pregnant women often do not realize what they are entitled to during the delivery, so it is worth paying attention to what women can expect from the staff during and after childbirth as well as what facilities may be used by pregnant women during their stay in the hospital.

Possibility of taking any position during the first and second stage of childbirth.

Even in the early 90's of the twentieth century, in almost all hospitals in Poland women were forced to remain in the horizontal position throughout the entire duration of labor. This position is undoubtedly the most suitable for intra-antenatal monitoring of the labor and the most convenient for medical personnel. However, numerous scientific reports from around the world undermine the sense of its use during labor. On the contrary, the benefits of vertical positions

(sitting, squatting, kneeling, standing) are more and more often emphasized. The issue of deviating from the routinely used supine position is also raised by Polish authors. As we read in one of the academic textbooks: *Recently, an uninhibited and spontaneous approach to normal birth has been recommended, where the mother herself chooses any position convenient for her, changing it voluntarily during childbirth, including the so-called squatting and left-sided position* [7].

The possibility to use various equipment to facilitate childbirth

- **Sack bag.** It is filled with tiny styrofoam balls, which allows you to adjust its shape to the most comfortable position that a woman chooses. Styrofoam captures the heat collected and heats the sore place, which is usually the lumbosacral spine. This causes vasodilation and increases the supply of oxygenated blood, which reduces pain.

- **Mattress.** It allows you to freely take on a variety of positions, including knee-elbow, squatting and other.

- **Childbirth chair.** Enables childbirth in a vertical position.

- **Ladder.** Delicate hanging on the ladder during contraction causes relief of the muscles of the back and lumbar area and straightening the spine, which significantly reduces the pain.

- **Rope.** It allows to obtain an effect comparable to hanging on a ladder.

- **Ball.** Using the ball has a multidirectional effect. The movement of the pelvis causes it to adapt to the child's head, not the other way round. In addition, moderate muscle work makes them better oxygenated, which reduces the sensation of pain. While using the ball, the crotch is also massaged.

The presence of a partner during childbirth often causes the mother to be calmer and helps with concentration, increases the sense of security and increases the comfort of childbirth. The partner helps controlling the regulated time of breathing and helps the mother to relax in the intervals between contractions. They help to stand, walk, kneel, sway and lift, bring water, massage painful places, comfort and surround their partner [6].

Childbirth in water

Benefits for the mother:

- homebathing relaxation,
- relaxation of the cervix and, in consequence, its faster opening,
- pelvic and crotch muscles relaxation,
- faster descent of the head in the genital canal,
- pain reduction,
- doses reduction of analgesics and diastolic drugs,
- easier to take any position,
- improvement of uteroplacental blood flow,
- reducing the effect of gravity,

- there is no evidence of a greater number of soft tissue injuries and infections during deliveries in water.

Benefits for a child:

- shortening the duration of the first and second period of childbirth,
- relieving the moment of decompression of the head in the final stage of the delivery period,
- the effect of a smooth transition (from water to water),
- constant temperature of the environment,
- lower impact of sound and light [6].

Recently, the term "bonding" is becoming more and more fashionable, which consists in creating the bonds between parents and the child as early as possible. It is a broader concept than "rooming-in", because it concerns not only the mother and the child, but the whole family. Currently, many hospitals have single rooms in which the mother, her partner and the newborn are present. In this way, the partner takes care of the mother and child, which facilitates quick connection between them and naturally develops the ability to care for the newborn.

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Conflict of interest:

The authors have declared no conflict of interest